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ESPOL: a change exalted by our strengths.

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ABSTRACT

Education is an important factor in the development of countries, and universities are committed to train professionals whose skills enable them to contribute to such development. In this context, ESPOL has generated a competency-based and student-centred education system. This system uses methodologies based on active learning and a series of activities, formal and informal, that develop significant learning for a solid technical education, soft skills and a tendency to long-life learning.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering education research, Curriculum development, Skills and engineering education.

Keywords: Curriculum development, active learning, significant learning, integral education.

INTRODUCTION

ESPOL is a university that continuously searches excellency. Curricular reforms have been a standard practice that consider their auto-imposed challenging goals, international standards, and the Ecuadorian regulation. It is a process of evaluation,

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updating, and contextualization of the academic activities of ESPOL, to promote the integral development of each student. The current reform seeks the generation of new knowledge and skills for students, promoting their adaptation to the demands of society, the innovations that affect the environment and the economic impulse that competent professionals give to a country, without neglecting our role of preparing future social leaders who are concerned about the collective benefit. In this context, the curricular reform fully implemented in 2017 will be described in this article.

1 EDUCATION SYSTEMS

1.1 Social constructivism and active learning

Active learning is based on the main principles of constructivism; however, they are not enough to explain it as the student-teacher interaction in a different way to create a student-centred classroom [1,2]. Constructivism was introduced by Jean Piaget and his followers, as a theory about the generation of knowledge, not only about learning or about education. It establishes learning as an interaction between the individuals who learns with the environment in which they develop [3]. Several experiences expect the apprentices to depart from what they know, and the teacher to guide the construction processes according to the collective knowledge.

Methodologies based on constructivism declare it is required to motivate students to analyse their experiences about the subject studied, also motivating them to propose a method for the learning of new knowledge according to their interest and capacities. The theory of constructivism also promotes that knowledge is generated in community, focusing on what students are capable to develop and the activities used by the teacher to stimulate and support the progress of students [4].

On the other hand, social constructivism of Vygotsky [5] indicates that cognitive development is influenced by the culture of the society and the strategies to solve problems through dialogue with other people from it, which concludes that knowledge is also the addition of knowledge of a person's own schema and its comparison with the schema of those surrounding him or her. This relates to a "zone of proximal development" (ZPD) which is the difference of what a student can do with help or without it. This theory says that abilities are more likely to develop by working with a guide or peer collaboration rather than a job on its own [6]. Therefore, the ZPD also depends on the scaffolding that supports a student supported by a tutor or by peers.

Since university students are not mere receptors of knowledge, modern universities work on the development of abilities related to the identification and problem solving, planning, auto criticism, and communication so that they support their opinions with evidence. Therefore, students are responsible of their own learning processes, empowered to learn out of classrooms, searching for information beyond what is presented to them. Consequently, universities educate professionals able to learn how to learn [7,8]. According to this, university students get involved in small groups working at their own pace, thinking about their own work, engaging in a creative and productive learning to solve problems, and guided by their teachers [9].

Significant Learning is a process in which students relate to new knowledge with information from their own, adapting and building over it [10]. Therefore, it occurs when students effectively relate their experiences with the knowledge received from lectures and applied it to solve problems of their professions. Active learning is a methodology that presents positive results to face the difficulties of learning [11]. However, master classes are still the predominant style even though they are inefficient to achieve significant learning. As expressed by Piaget, learning requires

other pedagogical relationships, defining the active auto-regulation. Active learning develops in environments where students: actively listen, communicate, observe, write with a clearly identified objective, effectively read and dramatize reflexively [2]. Active learning impels the significant learning through aspects such as: an inductive instructional design, activities that motivate discussions, collaborative work, constant feedback, real-life examples, active students constructing knowledge, a teacher as a guide, a student-based learning, and an elevated level of comprehension [11,12,13].

1.2 The millennials as higher education students

An important factor for learning is the type of student that confronts the contents and the construction of knowledge. At ESPOL we consider our students are members of the Z generation, meaning the postmillennial. This generation grew surrounded by technology, lives in a digital world, and is accustomed to use emerging technologies in their everyday lives. They are connected to technology and have access to computers, laptops, smartphones, among others [14]. This generation do and learn in a different way, which motivates a disconnection with the methods used by lecturers.

2 ESPOL

ESPOL was established in 1958 at Guayaquil, Ecuador. Three major moments in its history are: inauguration of National Centre for Aquaculture and Marine Research at 1990, reinforcing its vision toward research; inauguration of Campus Gustavo Galindo at 1991, relocating around 3500 students and offering around 700 hectares for present and future activities; and, at 1997 doubling enrolment of students with respect to 1991. Currently, it has around 12000 students in 33 undergraduate programs and 1000 in 16 graduate programs. 70% of undergraduate students belong to science and engineering programs and the rest are from administration, economics, graphic design, video production, tourism, process auditing and nutrition.

The curricular reform process takes place in an institution awarded with the highest categorization within the National System of Higher Education, both in 2009 and 2012, as well as the accreditation for the programs of mechanical engineering and computer science by ABET. Accreditation processes continue for all undergraduate programs at accreditation agencies according to the corresponding degrees.

ESPOL establish its main objective declaring its mission: “to form excellent, socially responsible professionals, leaders, entrepreneurs, with solid moral and ethical values that contribute to the scientific, technological, social, economic, environmental and political development of the country, and to serve society by carrying out research, innovating, promoting technology transfer and providing high quality services.”

ESPOL established a goal to be part of international rankings, integrating undergraduate and graduate education with research activities. This requires strengthening the institutional research system, generating more graduate programs, and reformulating our undergraduate degrees.

2.1 Successful practices

As part of the analysis for curricular reform, four main successful practices were reviewed. The first one is declaring graduate programs and research as a suitable institutional environment. Another one is a solid base in sciences as background to develop further professional knowledge. The third one is our culture of continuous improvement: formally declared in 2005, reinforced in 2008 with the practice of assessment for learning outcomes, and consolidated during accreditation processes for all programs with international agencies. Finally, to relate its excellence to

professors in continuous improvement: more full time members, with Ph.D. degree and experience in research projects.

2.2 The Ecuadorian context

Since 2007, Ecuadorian government guidelines have sought to strengthen national productive forces while promoting value chains linked to local endogenous development, integrating production processes with environmental factors and optimizing the use of renewable and non-renewable natural resources. In this context, current legislation is oriented to a humanistic, cultural and scientific education to develop integral, creative, responsible, critical, participatory and productive professionals. The system proposes to: a) promote academic quality and continuous improvement through evaluation and accreditation processes; b) contextualize education within the territories and their needs; c) impel creativeness, entrepreneurship, and bio-consciousness; and, d) strengthen the knowledge, application and research of science and technology.

The academic bylaws define education as diverse and integral, to provide an innovative, relevant and excellence-based service. Therefore, the programs offered by universities should meet the curricular requirements of our society, combining them with the soft skills required in the national planning documents. ESPOL also guided its curricular reform by advisory committees. Each program has an advisory committee with representation of its graduates and from employers, constituting a source of feedback for the program's curriculum and the student outcomes.

3 THE CURRICULAR REFORM AT ESPOL

ESPOL pursued a curricular reform to assure the deliverance of integral professionals with lifelong learning skills, as required in a world of constant and rapid changes [15,16] This need arises due to the geometric progression of scientific and technological knowledge [17]. For this, the reform settles a continuous monitoring of activities for students to experience a self-direct learning (in which they establish their goals), autonomous (in which they define how to govern their learning process), and self-regulated (with self-assessment and auto-corrective measures) [18].

ESPOL proposes a competences-based learning-teaching process with a student-centred focus, establishing reasoning as a fundamental characteristic of the cognitive process since *reasoning is a natural disposition based on the usage of language and [...] the rational element is present in all our behaviours, becoming a part of our most minimal mental functions* [19]. This guided the inclusion of two language courses in Spanish and five in English in all curricula, and the commitment to develop this area throughout the curriculum of all programs.

Our learning-teaching process is based on competences, establishing seven common competences to all programs called the institutional learning outcomes which become the stamp of our education. The development of such competences is not the sole responsibility of one or two courses. All the formation, including the institutional learning outcomes, is responsibility of a series of efforts joining curricular and extracurricular activities to impart knowledge, apply it and develop it.

The reform process as shown in *Fig. 1* displays the procedure followed to develop the programs. The relevance analysis was a cyclic process during which the advisory committees gave periodic feedback for educational objectives, learning outcomes and the curricula as well.

Fig. 1. Graphic representation of the curricular reform process.

The institutional core give a basis for ESPOL's distinctive imprint: reasoning, systemic thinking, bio-consciousness, entrepreneurship, problem solving and knowledge contextualization. It includes courses and activities such as complementary education including social and humanistic disciplines (psychology, history, politics, among others), arts (photography, music or body expression), and sports training (soccer, tennis, chess, kayak, among others). The seven institutional learning outcomes are related to: effective communication in Spanish and English, long-life learning, working in multidisciplinary teams, entrepreneurship abilities, understanding contemporary issues, and ethic and professional responsibility.

Development of formative research is part of the integration of undergraduate programs to research and graduate studies. This model provides students with basic tools and skills required for research (based on the scientific method), allowing them to identify and solve problems, oriented to the search for truth, forming them as high-level professionals [20]. ESPOL establishes a mandatory formative stage and a second stage based on a research itinerary that applies research-based learning.

The different areas of knowledge count with common courses ordered during the first year of the programs. Since Ecuadorian regulation requires a student to decide on a preferred program before entering university, common years are created to facilitate adaptation of new students and allow them to analyse their program choice, taking advantage of the institutional resources. Three general areas were designed for: engineering programs, arts, and social sciences. Due to particularities of their origins, undergraduate degrees for mathematics, nutrition and archaeology were excepted.

All programs offer projects, services and other activities to relate students with society. Students develop their pre-professional practices to apply knowledge in institutional, business or community environments, whether public or private. Their practices are monitored and assessed, providing feedback about student's abilities to explore, diagnose and experiment, as well as to intervene and solve problems.

Graduation process is based on capstone projects that validate knowledge, abilities and competences developed during programs. Within the projects, students work in groups, solving real problems framed in their professional practice. It is mandatory and it may include students from several programs to impel multidisciplinary teams. Another option is to participate in a research project led by Professors, and could be used for a special mention.

ESPOL plans master classes, practical work, laboratory sessions, field trip, autonomous work, tutoring activities, collaborative and cooperative work, pre-professional practices, and cultural events among others. They establish our philosophy: achievement of learning outcomes will depend on a combination of activities to empower students to develop knowledge, apply it and own it. Learning outcomes are assessed and valued through curricular routes. The routes establish the series of activities that show a formative contribution being responsible to instruct the different learning outcomes, as well as the ones used to evaluate them.

4 EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AT ESPOL

ESPOL visualizes the teaching-learning process as the execution of related activities. All activities are efforts for students to be recognized for their competence in technical areas, with solid humanistic foundation and able to continue learning. Assimilation of learning outcomes exceeds the responsibility of one or two courses, especially in outcomes concerning communication, teamwork, ethics, among others.

Several learning environments were created, based on learning strategies designed for specific objectives. The experience includes didactic material for key moments of the instructional process and moments to give feedback for students. Different initiatives include formal environments based on official evaluation of activities and learning outcomes, and informal environments which contribute to several outcomes (their contribution is measured but are not used to evaluate specific students).

The formal environments generated include aspects such as:

- Flipped classrooms: where lecturers do not transmit knowledge as done traditionally, but become facilitators in the construction of knowledge by students as collaborative researchers. Courses using this methodology are Physics (Peer Project Learning, PPL, and Research-Action Project, RAP), and English courses.
- Knowledge integration: where projects integrate knowledge, and assess learning outcomes. Each program establishes at least one course for each academic year so that several projects throughout the curricula challenge to integrate the knowledge of the different courses from those years and giving significant solutions to problems. A final integration course is the Capstone Course, in which learning outcomes are assessed and knowledge integration is monitored.
- Practical learning: where knowledge, abilities and capabilities are developed through activities such as laboratory sessions, field trips, or pre-professional practices. They focus on the implementation of analytical skills, decision making, as well as observation, diagnosis and group work oriented to collaboration.

Some formal initiatives are the *mini-businesses* within entrepreneurship courses to impel recognition of opportunities to add value to goods or processes; activities such as the BIDA fair (biology, research, development and application) within biology and environmental management courses to generate bio-consciousness; among others.

Informal activities focus their work to support formal activities to develop knowledge, abilities and capabilities. They are dynamic processes since they involve the direct participation of students from the beginning. Some examples are:

- Student clubs: multidisciplinary groups to develop within different areas. The diversity of clubs enriches the social, cultural and educational experiences.
- English clubs: informal environments to express freely while developing and improving communication abilities to speak, write, listen and comprehend.
- Writing centres: environments to enhance writing abilities in Spanish and English, focusing on the expression of proper reasoning through language.
- Ajá! Science Park: a park that offer stimulating experiences to explore science and engineering. The activities generate a fondness for the search of answers to question and the invention.

Another initiative is the Counselling system in which all students count with a lecturer as counsellor. This process allows a personalized monitoring of performance of students and give feedback for the programs. Also, affirmative actions are included to support minority groups, such as scholarships for low-income students or the development of specific activities for students with conditions like dyslexia, dysgraphia, speech apraxia, among others.

Professors and lecturers receive training to develop new curricula according to the reform guidelines. It begins with an induction process to understand the institution's philosophy, an accompaniment in classroom voluntarily requested, and a Teacher Training Program developed two years ago to improve pedagogical capacities. Currently the program includes eleven modules that cover: communication and reasoning process; macro and micro curricular planning; ethics; information and communication technologies; assessment and evaluation of learning; cooperative, collaborative and autonomous learning; research based learning, and entrepreneurship. More than three hundred teachers approved the program and around a hundred took some modules according to their needs. Another initiative is "Tertulias" which are cultural events such as cinema forum, read theatre, musical events, or conversation for a, organized by different departments to contribute to the integration of professors and lecturers.

The implementation of new curricula occurred in 2017, however, initiatives have been tested for a year or two. As preliminary results, it was observed that PPL methodology raised the approval rate of Physics C from 62.53 to 77.58%, while RAP methodology did it for Physics A and B from 44.35 to 78.55%. Standardized tests showed that students generated significant knowledge. Integration of undergraduate programs to research allowed 339 senior students during 2015 and 2016 in research projects, of which 93 did so as their graduation process. Also, capstone courses graduated more than 1600 professionals during the same period, representing 23% of the graduated professionals from 2012 to 2016.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of a student-centred education is a challenge for students and professors. However, the institutional support for the initiatives allowed access to resources and asses their effectiveness. Preliminary results, as well as the opinion of students monitored through counselling sessions and focus groups, show that new methodologies are appreciated not only for the improvement of approval rates but since they have a positive impact on students, improving their reading comprehension, communication abilities and analysis of information. Our future work includes a longitudinal study of the methodologies implemented and their effect on the knowledge, abilities and capacities developed by our students.

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